

Relationship among Leisure Satisfaction, Spiritual Wellness, and Self-Esteem of Older Adults

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Abstract—This study sought to determine whether there were relationships existed among leisure satisfaction, self-esteem, and spiritual wellness. Four hundred survey instruments were distributed, and 334 effective instruments were returned, for an effective rate of 83.5%. The participants were recruited from a purposive sampling that subjects were at least 60 years of age and retired in Tainan City, Taiwan. Three instruments were used in this research: Leisure Satisfaction Scale (LSS), Self-Esteem Scale (SES), and Spirituality Assessment Scale (SAS). The collected data were analyzed statistically. The findings of this research were as follows: 1. There is significantly correlated between leisure satisfaction and spiritual wellness. 2. There is significantly correlated between leisure satisfaction and self-esteem. 3. There is significantly correlated between spiritual wellness and self-esteem.

Keywords—Leisure satisfaction, spiritual wellness, self-esteem.

I. INTRODUCTION

DUE to rising life expectancy and declining birth rate, Taiwan has become one of the fastest aging societies in the world. From 2010 to 2030, the number of older people is projected to increase by 114%. Moreover, the population aged 60 and over, which is the group most likely to need health and long-term care services [1]. Therefore, how to decrease prevalence rates of chronic diseases, instead of establishing and maintaining mental and physical functioning can be a challenge to reduce social economic burden and make people live more healthily of older ages, that has becoming a critical issue for any developing countries around the world.

Leisure implies time to do something without obligation or duty, and doing what an individual desire. The term of leisure has been identified as “free or unobligated time, time during which work, life-sustaining functions, and other obligatory activities are not performed” [2]. There are many benefits associated with being leisurely lifestyle. Leisure can be more satisfying than work, as well as a significant antecedent to pleasure and achievement. Further, engaging in leisure

behavior may have a positive influence on a variety of other outcomes including physical, emotional, spiritual, and psychological wellness [3].

In general, leisure satisfaction refers to the “positive perception or feeling that an individual forms, elicits or even gains as a result of engaging in leisure and choice” [4]. Several variables have been linked to leisure satisfaction, in particular, personality, leisure participation, leisure motivation, leisure interest, life satisfaction and constraints to leisure, as well as various domain related satisfactions. Comparing to the literature on leisure and social wellness in later life, less effort has been made to focus on the influences upon spiritual wellness, and self-esteem for this older age group.

Wellness commonly considered as many dimensions, such as physical, psychological, emotional, social, and intellectual wellness. Wellness is not merely implies for health or fitness, in fact, an individual can be physically disabled or mentally retarded, yet still possess an excellent wellness spirituality. Spirituality can be thought of as “an awareness of a being or force that transcends the material aspects of life and gives a deep sense of wholeness or connectedness to the universe” [5]. Spiritual wellness is a personal matter involving values, faith and belief that provide an individual’s to create and discover meaning and purpose of human existence. Frequency of leisure participation and level of leisure satisfaction were found to be positively associated with overall perceived wellness, including spiritual wellness [6].

Self-esteem has been identified as “how one feels about oneself concept in comparison to an ideal” [7]. A challenge in later life is to maintain a strong sense of self-identity when experiencing such as roles, contacts and positions change. However, the changes that occur through life may impact an individual’s self-esteem, especially when people retire from occupation. One of the negative aspects of retirement is the lack of emphasis on self-reliance, which may lead elders to become depressed. Participating in leisure activities are not just improving one’s appearance, self-confidence, and physical fitness, but contributing to maintain positive self-esteem [8]. Therefore, satisfying leisure experiences by regularly participating in leisure activities can be a major component to result of successful aging.

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II. METHODOLOGY

The primary purpose of this study was to investigate the correlations between leisure satisfaction, spiritual wellness and self-esteem. The results were based on the collection and analysis obtained from traditional Chinese versions of Leisure Satisfaction Scale (LSS), Self-Esteem Scale (SES), and Spirituality Assessment Scale (SAS) given to participants.

A. Data Collection

Participants were from a purposive sample of 334 aged people, who were at least 60 years of age and retired. The participants were involved in a variety of locations (parks, churches, temples, senior centers, and school playgrounds) where a majority of Tainan City senior groups gathered.

B. Instrument

The instrument used in this study consisting of three components, in which including Leisure Satisfaction Scale (LSS), Spirituality Assessment Scale (SES), and Self-Esteem Scale (SAS).

Leisure Satisfaction Scale was designed by Ragheb and Beard [9]. Five-point Likert Scale was used to measure the extent to which individuals perceived that their personal needs are met through leisure activities. This scale is composed of 24 items, and is divided into six dimensions: psychological, social, educational, relaxational, physiological, and aesthetic.

Spirituality Assessment Scale was developed by Howden [10]. There are four categories in this scale: purpose in life, appreciation for depth of life, expanse of the universe, and operating natural forces. These four categories are consisted of 28 identified items. Six-point Likert Scale was used for the assessment of both individual and congregational spiritual well-being.

Self-Esteem Scale was modified by Lin [11] that was widely used to examine situation of one's own self-esteem. There are four categories in this scale: social value, family value, physical ability, and self-ability. These four categories are consisted of 22 identified items which are scored on a five-point Likert Scale.

C. The null hypotheses posited here was:

1. There are no significant correlations between each dimension of leisure satisfaction (psychological, educational, social, relaxational, physiological and aesthetic) and each dimension of spiritual wellness, which include purpose in life, appreciation for depth of life, expanse of the universe, operating and natural forces.
2. There are no significant correlations between each dimension of leisure satisfaction and self-esteem which include social value, family value, physical- ability and self-ability.
3. There are no significant correlations between each dimension of spiritual wellness and each dimension of self-esteem.

D. Data Analysis

The SPSS 12.0 was used to analyze the data. The Alpha coefficient was conducted for the study components by utilizing leisure satisfaction, spiritual wellness, and self-esteem scales for all subjects in order to test instrumental reliability. Cronbach's α is commonly used to measure the internal reliability and internal of a scale. Nunnally and Bernstein suggested that Cronbach's alpha values above 0.7 are acceptable for psychometric scales [12]. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to examine null hypotheses. In addition, descriptive statistics were also used to examine the demographics of sample.

III. RESULT

A total of 400 aged people were surveyed. Sixty-six surveys were unusable; this number includes 53 surveys which were not returned and 13 surveys which were incomplete. Thus, 334 subjects were used for analysis (83.5 % response rate). The Alpha coefficient for the Leisure Satisfaction Scale was .96, the Spirituality Assessment Scale was .97, and Self-Esteem Scale was .93. Therefore, these survey instruments were considered very reliable. Demography of participants is shown in Table I. In addition, Mean score for each category of leisure satisfaction, spiritual wellness, and self-esteem are shown in Table II.

TABLE I
 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE PARTICIPANTS

Variables		F	%
Gender	Men	170	50.9
	Women	164	49.1
Age	60-64	130	37.7
	65-69	252	41.3
	70 or above	196	21.0
Health status	Excellent	70	21.0
	Better than average	128	38.3
	About average	120	35.9
	Worse than average	16	4.8
Economic status	prosperous	6	1.8
	Better than average	262	78.4
	About average	64	19.2
	Worse than average	2	0.6
Marital status	Single	18	5.4
	Married	286	85.6
	Widowed	18	5.4
	Divorced or separated	12	3.6
Reason of retirement	Age limitation	120	35.9
	Illness	10	3.0
	Voluntary	92	27.5
	Others	112	33.5
Years from retirement	3 or below	176	52.7
	3-5	66	19.8
	6-8	34	10.2
	8 or above	58	17.4

Note. N =334.

TABLE II
 MEAN SCORE OF LEISURE SATISFACTION, SPIRITUAL WELLNESS, AND SELF-ESTEEM

Variables	Leisure satisfaction	Spiritual wellness	Self-esteem
Mean	3.64	4.56	3.65

Note. N =334.

Table III indicated that there is significant correlation between each dimension of leisure satisfaction and spiritual wellness, and the correlation coefficients was positively correlated ($p < .001$) and have median correlations at least ($r > .468$, $p < .001$). While the overall leisure satisfaction have higher correlations with dimensions of the appreciation for depth of life ($r = .701$), the expanse of the universe ($r = .749$), and overall spiritual wellness ($r = .744$). Therefore, hypothesis 1 was totally rejected.

TABLE III

PEARSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION FOR EACH DIMENSION OF LEISURE SATISFACTION AND SPIRITUAL WELLNESS

Spiritual wellness \ Leisure satisfaction	Purpose in life	Appreciation for depth of life	Expanse of the universe	Operating natural forces	Spiritual wellness
Psychological	.554***	.602***	.564***	.480***	.601***
Educational	.606***	.688***	.614***	.570***	.679***
Social	.545***	.585***	.700***	.468***	.633***
Relaxational	.599***	.557***	.677***	.492***	.631***
Physiological	.619***	.590***	.686***	.485***	.647***
	.644***	.569***	.623***	.510***	.631***
Leisure satisfaction	.693***	.701***	.749***	.586***	.744***

Note. *** $p < .001$.
 $N = 334$.

Table IV indicated that there is significant correlation between each dimension of leisure satisfaction and self-esteem, and that was positively correlated ($p < .001$), the correlation coefficients are between .40 to .69. Overall leisure satisfaction had the highest correlation with overall self-esteem ($r = .670$). Results showed that each dimension of leisure satisfaction and self-esteem have median correlations. Therefore, hypothesis 2 was also rejected.

TABLE IV

PEARSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION FOR EACH DIMENSION OF LEISURE SATISFACTION AND SELF-ESTEEM

Leisure satisfaction \ Self-esteem	Social value	Family value	Physical-ability	Self-ability	Self-esteem
Psychological	.542***	.459***	.486***	.510***	.568***
Educational	.500***	.484***	.385***	.483***	.532***
Social	.564***	.521***	.457***	.579***	.603***
Relaxational	.514***	.494***	.391***	.556***	.555***
Physiological	.570***	.545***	.483***	.596***	.623***
Aesthetic	.518***	.479***	.484***	.550***	.572***
Leisure satisfaction	.623***	.579***	.521***	.634***	.670***

Note. *** $p < .001$.
 $N = 334$.

Table V indicated that there is significant correlation between each dimension of spiritual wellness and self-esteem, and the correlation coefficients was positively correlated ($r > .44$, $p < .001$). Findings demonstrated that each dimension of spiritual wellness and self-esteem have median correlations at least. While the overall spiritual wellness had the highest correlation with social value ($r = .716$). Overall spiritual wellness had the second highest correlation with overall self-esteem ($r = .709$). Therefore, hypothesis 3 was rejected.

TABLE V

PEARSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION FOR EACH DIMENSION OF SPIRITUAL WELLNESS AND SELF-ESTEEM

Spiritual wellness \ Self-esteem	Social value	Family value	Physical-ability	Self-ability	Self-esteem
Purpose in life	.647***	.547***	.477***	.493***	.633***
Appreciation for depth of life	.695***	.584***	.502***	.528***	.676***
Expanse of the universe	.685***	.621***	.453***	.632***	.691***
Operating natural forces	.594***	.510***	.444***	.503***	.594***
Spiritual wellness	.716***	.620***	.510***	.593***	.709***

Note. *** $p < .001$.
 $N = 334$.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicated that significant relationships existed among leisure satisfaction, spiritual wellness, and self-esteem in older adults in Taiwan. Relationships between each dimension of leisure satisfaction (psychological, educational, social, relaxational, physiological and aesthetic) and each dimension of spiritual wellness, which include purpose in life, appreciation for depth of life, expanse of the universe, operating and natural forces were positive correlated. The association between leisure satisfaction and spiritual wellness is consistent with previous findings of Heintzman in 2002 [13]. One explanation is that being an active leisurely lifestyle may increase opportunity to interact and socialize with others which result in improving and maintaining spiritual well-being through satisfying leisure experiences.

Each dimension of leisure satisfaction also positively associated with self-esteem wellness, including social value, family value, physical-ability, and self-ability. Older adults may be experiencing a change in roles such as retirement, grandparenthood, and increased isolation, in addition to declining health. Participation in sport-related activities fosters an individual to construct and establish positive body images, enhance perceptions of physical competence and predict higher self-esteem [14]. The needs of both perceived competence and self-determination simultaneously positively contribute to leisure satisfaction [15]. Therefore, leisure satisfaction can be regarded as component to influence one's self-esteem.

The Department of Health investigated the situation of melancholia by using Taiwanese Depression Scale for 3,929 participants in 2007. The results demonstrated that the older adults aged between of 55 to 64 suffered from depression were 12.9%, while aged between of 65 to 74 were 20.2% [16]. Depression is a common problem of older adults, and is believed to be caused by low self-esteem and lack of a spiritual connection and purpose. Low self-esteem usually accompanies with negative emotions such as depression and anxiety. Positive spirituality has been found to be linked with health in effective partnerships between the spiritual wellness and self-esteem. Low self-esteem is associated with many mental health problems. However, spirituality can contribute to mental health, mental illness and recovery [17].

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